

Advances in the chemistry of Friedel-Crafts acylation

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The scope and application of Friedel-Crafts reactions have proliferated tremendously. The advances in Friedel-Crafts acylation reactions in areas such as regioselective synthesis, new synthetic methods, cycloacylation, synthesis of secondary products of acylation of arenes, stereoselective and other miscellaneous syntheses are reviewed. Developments in Friedel-Crafts catalysts including Lewis and Brønsted acids, Brønsted-Lewis super acids and zeolites in relation to their utility in the discovery of regioselective and high yield synthetic technology are discussed.

Charles Friedel and James Mason Crafts discovered in 1877 that anhydrous AlCl_3 could be used as a condensing agent for the synthesis of an infinite number of hydrocarbons. Not only of AlCl_3 , they also reported the use of ferric and zinc chlorides as well as double salt of sodium aluminium chloride but that these were less reactive than AlCl_3 . During their fourteen years' work in this area they extended their studies to various fields, viz. reactions of organic halides and unsaturated compounds with aromatic and aliphatic hydrocarbons; reactions of anhydrides of organic acids with aromatic hydrocarbons; reactions of oxygen, sulfur, sulfur dioxide, carbon dioxide and phosgene with aromatic hydrocarbons; cracking of aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons; and polymerization of unsaturated hydrocarbons. Thus even in the early stage of the discovery the wide scope of the reaction was realized. During the last 120 years the scope and application of the reaction have proliferated tremendously covering every conceivable variation of reagent, catalyst and reaction parameters. A number of electrophilic reactions are now classified as Friedel-Crafts type reactions¹. These reactions include not only formation of carbon-carbon bonds but also carbon-oxygen, carbon-nitrogen, carbon-sulfur, carbon-halogen, carbon-phosphorus, carbon-deuterium, carbon-boron and many other types of bonds.

Friedel-Crafts-type reactions have been widely employed in organic synthesis for effecting alkylation, dealkylation, acylation, isomerization, polymerization, sulfonation, sulfonation, sulfonation, sulfonation, nitration, perchlorylation, halogenation, hydroxylation, amination and many other reactions. Many industrial processes such as the production of high octane gasoline, ethylbenzene, synthetic rubber, and detergent alkylates are based on Friedel-Crafts-type reactions. A voluminous literature on the subject has been accumulated which has mostly been covered by monographs^{2,3} and comprehensive reviews⁴.

However, the progress in Friedel-Crafts chemistry is still remarkable and advances in this area are frequently reported.

Although there are apparently wide variety of types, Friedel-Crafts reactions can be broadly divided into two general categories, alkylations and acylations. Within these two categories there is considerable diversity. This review is concerned with the recent advances in the Friedel-Crafts acylation reaction and covers literature of the last two decades.

Acylation of aromatics

Friedel-Crafts acylations of aromatics are of considerable importance because of their wide practical applications. Acylating agents in general are more reactive than alkylating agents, and the acylation reaction of acyl halides with aromatic compounds in presence of Friedel-Crafts catalyst proceeds readily. Electronegative groups if present in the aromatics have an inhibiting effect. Although it is difficult to introduce more than one acyl group into an aromatic ring, diacylated products have been prepared using strenuous conditions. With an excess of reagents, diacetyl durene **1** and diacetyl isodurene **2** were prepared⁵. The diketones **1** and **2** have been reported to be formed in more

than 90% yields from the corresponding hydrocarbons, if an excess of acylating agent and especially if an excess of catalyst over the acylating reagent is employed. Products arising from methyl migration prior to acetylation are also formed.

Buckley III and Rapoport⁶ investigated the relationships between electrophile reactivity and catalyst stoichiometry on the yield and nature of products from aryl ether acylation. They used AlBr_3 as the catalyst which is slightly more reactive and readily prepared and easily purified just before use. They observed that acylation of alkyl aryl ethers was dependent on the stoichiometry of the Friedel-Crafts catalyst. When 100 mol% catalyst was used, acylation proceeded rapidly and in high yield. The reaction was essentially completely arrested with large molar excess of catalyst. This inhibition could be reversed by using sterically bulky alkyl groups which apparently effectively prevented complexing between catalyst and aryl ether. Based on these observations, the authors developed processes for regioselective intramolecular acylation of either a phenyl or an alkoxyphenyl ring when both are present.

In Friedel-Crafts acylations generally predominant *para*-substitution is observed which is considered to be a consequence of steric *ortho*-hindrance to the acylating agent. Olah *et al.*⁷ showed in their work on Friedel-Crafts benzylation, a relationship between the electrophilicity of the reagent and the nucleophilicity of the substrate and positional selectivity. Their subsequent study⁸ on Friedel-Crafts acylation of benzene and toluene with substituted acyl halides for the determination of the effect of substituents in the acylating agents showed that both substrate selectivity as expressed by ($k_{\text{Toluene}} : k_{\text{Benzene}}$ rate ratios) and positional selectivity (*ortho* : *para* ratio) were governed by the nature of the electrophiles. The results were explained by assuming that the position of the transition state of highest energy lies earlier along the reaction coordinate for reaction with stronger electrophiles and later with weaker electrophiles, resembling more in the former case, the starting aromatics (π complexes) and in the latter the Wheland intermediates (σ complexes).

Interesting kinetic studies made by Dehaan *et al.*⁹ on the substituent effects in Friedel-Crafts benzylation may be mentioned. The studies relate to the reaction of benzyl chloride with benzene and/or toluene catalyzed by TiCl_4 in nitromethane and in nitrobenzene and catalyzed by SbCl_5 in nitromethane and sulfolane. The reactions were all zero order in aromatic, first order in benzyl chloride, and either second order in TiCl_4 or first order in SbCl_5 . Competitively determined $k_{\text{Toluene}}/k_{\text{Benzene}}$ values and product toluene isomer percentages for all four reactions indicated that the reactions did not fit Brown's selectivity relationship (BSR)¹⁰. Competitive or noncompetitive kinetic studies were also reported for Friedel-Crafts benzylation reactions with *p*-chloro, 3,4-dichloro, *p*-methyl and *p*-nitrobenzyl chlorides in nitromethane. The AlCl_3 -catalyzed reactions of *p*-chloro- and 3,4-dichlorobenzyl chloride were both zero

order in aromatic and did not fit BSR. However, the TiCl_4 -catalyzed *p*-xylyl chloride reactions fitted Brown's relationship even though it was zero order in aromatic. The *p*-nitrobenzyl chloride reaction catalyzed by AlCl_3 was first order in aromatic hydrocarbon and also obeyed Brown's relationship. These mechanistic differences were rationalized in terms of Jencks' approach¹¹. Thus xylyl cation was thought to be diffusionally equilibrated and showed relatively high substrate selectivity. The less stable *p*-chloro- and 3,4-dichlorobenzyl cations reacted faster than they diffused thus exhibiting little selectivity. With *p*-nitrobenzyl chloride an $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ displacement mechanism was preferred.

Regioselective synthesis

Hyatt and Reynolds¹² showed that acyl fluoride- BF_3 system exhibited exceptional regioselectivity in the acylation of certain polycyclic aromatic substrates. Acenaphthene 3 reacts with electrophiles to give usually 5-substituted acenaphthenes as major products with minor products including 3-isomers which are difficult to isolate. Thus when substrate 3 was subjected to react with isobutyryl chloride- AlCl_3 in CH_2Cl_2 , the 5-substituted derivative 4 and 3-substituted isomer 5 were formed in the ratio 80 : 20. However, 3 reacted with isobutyryl fluoride- BF_3 in CH_2Cl_2 to give 4 and 5 in the ratio 15 : 85, and pure product 5 was obtained in 65% yield by recrystallization (eq. 1).

The authors¹² also demonstrated that 2-methylnaphthalene 6 on acylation with isobutyryl fluoride- BF_3 in CH_2Cl_2 gave 2-acyl-6-methylnaphthalene 7 in excellent yields (eq. 2).

This Friedel-Crafts method of acylation by which a variety of 3-substituted acenaphthenes and 2,6-disubstituted naphthalenes can be prepared has potential in organic synthesis.

Regioselective Friedel-Crafts acylations of 2(3*H*)-benzoxazolones 8^{13,14} and 2(3*H*)-benzothiazolones 9¹⁵ using AlCl_3 -*N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) are interesting. This process was found to proceed with high regioselectivity giving 6-acyl derivatives as the only isolable products from the reaction medium in appreciable yields. The ratio of AlCl_3 -DMF and the substrate are reported to be critical. The acylation was found to proceed with a satisfactory rate and yield of the product when this ratio was in the range 7-11¹⁵. This phenomenon is understandable in the light of

the observation made by Shen *et al.*¹⁶ who suggested that there are circumstances where the substrate is more extensively complexed to the Lewis acid than the electrophile-generating species. The use of donor ligands in combination with AlCl_3 was proposed to alleviate this problem. In such a condition the aromatic substrate will be complexed in a lesser extent to the AlCl_3 .

The other examples of the use of donor ligands in combination with AlCl_3 for regioselective Friedel-Crafts acylation are $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CS}_2$, $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-DMSO}$ and $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-DMF}$. Acylation of 2-substituted 1,4-benzodioxin derivatives **10** using $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CS}_2$ provided regioselectively the 6-acyl compounds. The same reaction with saturated analogs **11** af-

forded regioisomers with 7-acyl compounds predominating¹⁷. Mata and Suarez¹⁸ reported the use of $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-DMSO}$ and $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-DMF}$ for acylation of **10** and **11**. They observed that substrates **10** afforded the C-7 monoacylated product as the major or the only isolated product and substrates **11** furnished the C-6 monoacylated product as the major isomer, in a ratio that depends on the C-2 substituent.

Calixarenes have been investigated as host molecules and enzyme mimics, especially with appropriate functional groups¹⁹. Studies on electrophilic substitution of 26,28-dialkoxycalix[4]arenes revealed that the reactions took place at the *para*-positions of phenol rings²⁰⁻²². Selective Friedel-Crafts acylation of 26,28-dimethoxycalix[4]arene **12** with acyl chlorides in nitrobenzene afforded the diacylated products **13** in good to excellent yields²³. The substitution took place exclusively at *para*-positions of the phenol rings (eq. 3).

New synthetic methodology

A novel Friedel-Crafts reaction was discovered for the synthesis of 4-phenylnaphthalen-1-ols²⁴ which are drawing attention for their multiple biological activities. Veratrole **14** reacted with succinyl chloride under the catalytic effect of AlCl_3 at 60° in $\text{ClCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}$ as the solvent affording diketone **15** in a very low yield. The same reaction at low temperature (-10° to -5°) gave lactone **16** as the major product. The formation of lactone **16** is expected as succinyl chloride is known to exist in cyclic and acyclic forms (**17a** and **17b**), the former prevailing at low temperature. The lactone **16** on prolonged treatment (overnight) with BBr_3 furnished 4-phenylnaphthalen-1-ol **18** in 53% yield²⁴ (eq. 4). The generation of compound **18** from lactone **16**

has been rationalized. Reaction of several benzene derivatives with succinyl chloride at low temperature afforded the corresponding lactones as the major products which on prolonged treatment with BBr_3 gave the desired 4-phenylnaphthalen-1-ols²⁴.

Sequential and regioselective Friedel-Crafts reaction of *gem*-dihalocyclopropanecarbonyl chlorides with benzenes for the synthesis of 4-aryl-1-naphthol derivatives²⁵ is a novel approach. One of the sequential Friedel-Crafts reactions involved an intramolecular cyclization of *E*-3-aryl-2,2-dihalocyclopropanecarbonyl chlorides followed by intermolecular coupling with substituted benzenes giving 4-aryl-3-halo-1-naphthols. For example, *E*-2,2-dichloro-1-methyl-3-phenylcyclopropanecarbonyl chloride **19** with benzene in presence of AlCl_3 (2.2 eq.) gave 3-chloro-2-methyl-4-phenyl-1-naphthol **20** in 52% yield. It was demonstrated that during this sequential Friedel-Crafts reaction, intramolecular cyclization precedes intermolecular coupling with another benzene (eq. 5).

It was noted that the cyclopropane ring opening proceeded with high regioselectivity resulting in the selective syn-

thesis of 20. This method was used for the synthesis of various 4-aryl-3-halo-1-naphthols.

Another sequential Friedel-Crafts reaction involved the intermolecular acylation of 2,2-dihalo-1-cyclopropanecarbonyl chlorides 21 with one benzene molecule giving ketones 22, a subsequent intermolecular trap by another benzene molecule, and a final intramolecular cyclization (eq. 6). The reactions took place in a one-pot manner to give 4-phenyl-1-naphthols 23 with a highly regioselective bond b-cleavage. A variety of 23 were synthesized by step-wise incorporation of different substituted benzenes²⁵.

Talapatra *et al.*²⁶ reported very recently a simple one-pot synthesis of 10-methylbenzo[*a*]fluoranthene in good yield by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of 9-fluorenone.

A new synthesis of spirobenzopyran of biological interest has been accomplished²⁷ by Friedel-Crafts reaction of various *m*-dihydroxybenzenes and cycloalkylidene acetic acid in the presence of a Lewis acid. *m*-Dihydroxybenzenes 24 having different substituents were reacted with cycloalkylidene acetic acids 25 (*n* = 1 to 3) in the presence of a Lewis acid, i.e. ZnCl₂ + POCl₃ to give 2-spirobenzopyrans 26 in good yields (eq. 7).

Cycloacylation

Intramolecular cycloacylation of an aromatic compound bearing an acyl halide group in presence of AlCl₃ yields hydrindones, tetralones, chromones, xanthenes, etc. Cyclization of aromatics containing ketoacyl chlorides produces coumarandiones, chromandiones, indandiones and anthraquinones. Cyclization of acids catalyzed by hydrogen fluoride also leads to the formation of cyclic ketones. Intermolecular cycloacylation involving bifunctional acylating agents readily takes place to give desired products. Anthraquinones are synthesized by various methods. Among the most common synthetic approaches is the AlCl₃-mediated Friedel-Crafts reaction in which the phthalic anhydrides are condensed with various aromatic compounds and subsequently cyclized with hot sulfuric acid to produce the anthraquinones. Danielsen²⁸ employed this method for preparation of a number of anthraquinones

including a novel one 27 which was synthesized by condensation of 3-hydroxyphthalic anhydride 28 and 1,2-dimethoxybenzene 29 (eq. 8).

A facile one-step synthesis of spiro[4.5]deca-6,9-diene-2,8-dione 30 along with the normal product 6-methoxy-β-tetralone 31 from *p*-methoxyphenylacetyl chloride 32 via a Friedel-Crafts acylation followed by ring closure was reported²⁰. The best reaction conditions examined for the formation of the spirodienone 30 were found to be 2-2.5 equivalents of AlCl₃ at -30° (eq. 9).

Cephalotaxine 33, an alkaloid with an unusual 1-azaspiro[4.4]nonane moiety fused to a benzazepine system has attracted much attention because its simple ester derivatives exhibit significant antileukemic activity³⁰. A

Friedel-Crafts cyclization approach toward cephalotaxine was reported by Sha *et al.*³¹. An intramolecular cyclization of compound 34 in polyphosphoric acid smoothly afforded the cephalotaxine skeleton 35 in good yield with some recovered starting material (eq. 10).

The intramolecular Friedel-Crafts acylation of 2-(3-indolylthio)propionic acid **36** was found to undergo an unprecedented rearrangement to provide a novel tricyclic indole **37** having the sulfur substituted on C-4 rather than on the expected C-3. A mechanism for this rearrangement was proposed³². This rearrangement also proceeded with good optical retention when a chiral substrate was used. Thus this rearrangement has potential to be a non-racemic approach to this type of compounds.

Total synthesis of the microbial metabolite tolypocladin **38** and isotolypocladin **39** was achieved using Friedel-Crafts acylation for condensation of the 2-aza-anthra-

quinone-(9,10) ring³³. The condensation of 1,2,4-trimethoxybenzene **40** and 2-methylpyridine 4,5-dicarboxylic acid anhydride **41** under Friedel-Crafts conditions led to the formation of key products **42** and **43**, the acylation occurring regioselectively at position 5 of **40**. The products **42** and **43** which could be separated by recrystallization were converted to **38** and **39**, respectively, by cyclization and demethylation by H_2SO_4 (eq. 11).

β -Dicarbonyl compounds **44** ($R = \text{H, Me, OMe}$; $R_1 = \text{OEt, Me}$) have been used as substrates to react with methoxyacetyl chloride in presence of AlCl_3 in dry nitromethane for the highly selective synthesis of ethyl-1-oxo-2-indanecarboxylates and 1-oxo-2-acetylindanes **45**³⁴ (eq. 12). These products are useful synthons for many

natural and biologically active compounds. The process which seems to have an edge over other approaches to these products involves methoxymethylation of the substrates followed by cycloalkylation.

Intramolecular Friedel-Crafts acylation of the furan ring has been accomplished³⁵ with stannic chloride for both furyl isomers **46**, **47** of butyryl acid chloride giving the products **48** and **49** in good yields (eq. 13). The propionyl

chloride isomers, however, did not produce reasonable quantities of the cyclic ketone. Compounds **48** and **49** are useful intermediates for the preparation of valuable pharmaceuticals.

A new and general anionic equivalent of the Friedel-Crafts reaction for the regioselective synthesis of substituted and condensed fluorenones including aza analogues from biaryls and *m*-teraryl-2-amides has been developed by Fu *et al.*³⁶. For example, sequential LDA-induced cyclization and selective deisopropylation of compound **50** furnished dengibsinin **51**, a naturally occurring fluorenone (eq. 14).

A convenient procedure was developed for the synthesis of aryl and polycyclic-1-tetralones using as key steps the Suzuki coupling between the aromatic bromoderivative and the appropriate alkyl borane followed by intramolecular Friedel-Crafts acylation³⁷. The method appears to be quite general and compatible with different substitution in the aromatic ring.

Secondary acylation products of arenes

Mahato *et al.*³⁸ reported for the first time in the long history of Friedel-Crafts acylation of arenes that employment of excess amounts of substrates such as anisole **52** and phenetole **53** leads to the formation of polynuclear compounds as secondary reaction products. Thus one

molar proportion of dichloroacetyl chloride reacted with more than two molar proportion of **52** and **53** in the presence of 1.5-2 molar quantity of anhydrous AlCl_3 and furnished 2,2-dichloro-1,1-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)ethane **54**, 2,2-dichloro-1,1-bis(4-ethoxyphenyl)ethane **55**, 2,2-dichloro-1,1-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)ethane **56**, 2,2-dichloro-1,1-bis(4-ethoxyphenyl)ethane **57**, 1,1,2,2-tetrakis(4-methoxyphenyl)ethane **58** and 1,1-bis(4-ethoxyphenyl) ethylene **59**. No solvent was used as both anisole **52** and phenetole **53** are liquids and the reactions were carried out at ambient temperature. The formation of the unexpected products was rationalized.

Initial *p*-acylation of anisole **52** leads to the formation of the *p*-dichloroacylated product as an intermediate in the reaction. In the second step, a nucleophilic attack by a second molecule of the arene on the carbonyl group of dichloroacetyl anisole which is activated by the formation of a polar complex with AlCl_3 generates the intermediate cationic species **60**. While elimination of the proton geminal to the two chlorine atoms in **60** yields **54**, an intermolecular hydride shift generates **56** (Scheme 1). That the

normal dichloroacylated products were formed as intermediates was demonstrated by isolation after 2-4 h from the start of the reaction, although these normal products were not obtained at the end of the reaction, i.e. after 24 h from the start of the reaction. Formation of **58** was assumed to have arisen via stepwise or simultaneous alkylation of 2 mol of **53** by **54**. The product corresponding to **58** was not formed by phenetole **53** and instead compound **59** was isolated. This difference in behavior was ascribed to the difference in nucleophilicity of **52** and **53**, the latter being less nucleophilic. The process of hydrogenolysis was invoked for the formation of **59**.

Scheme 1

Subsequently, Roberts *et al.*³⁹ reported that mesitylene **61** reacts with acetyl chloride in the presence of AlCl_3 to form 1,1-dimesitylene **62**. Here also the normal acylation product was demonstrated to be an intermediate in the reaction. Mesitylene was also shown to react similarly with propionyl chloride forming 1,1-dimesitylpropene **63**, propiomesitylene being an intermediate. The formation of the unexpected dimeric products was attributed to the strenuous reaction conditions employed. The steric and electronic factors responsible for this unique Friedel-Crafts reaction were also discussed³⁹. These authors extended their study employing arenes of different steric and electronic properties⁴⁰, e.g. durene, isodurene and prehnitene **64**. While both durene and isodurene react with acetyl chloride and propionyl chloride under similar conditions forming 1,1-didurylene **65**, 1,1-didurylpropene **66** and 1,1-diisodurylene **67**, 1,1-diisodurylpropene **68**, respectively, prehnitene **64** with these acylating agents

gave only the normal acylated products 69 and 70. This different behavior of acylprehnitene was explained in terms of combined steric and electronic effects. The two *ortho*-methyl groups in acyldurene and acylisodurene prevent coplanarity of the carbonyl with the aromatic ring. A positive charge on the carbonyl carbon cannot be dissipated into the ring as it is possible in an acyl prehnitene, which has only one *ortho*-methyl group. However, invocation of the steric effect in the formation of the unexpected secondary products seems to be in doubt. *p*-Acylanisole and *p*-acylphenetole did form the secondary products although these acylated compounds do not have *ortho*-groups responsible for any steric effect.

Mahato *et al.*⁴¹ demonstrated in their work with substrates of varying nucleophilicity that formation of the unexpected secondary reaction products depends on the nucleophilicity of the arene and electrophilicity of the acyl carbonyl group of the initially formed acylated product. Application of higher temperature was necessary to induce dichloroacylation and subsequent secondary reactions for substrates with lower nucleophilicity. Among the substrates used, 1,3-dimethoxybenzene 71 with the greatest degree of nucleophilicity yielded the products of considerable interest, viz. 1,1,2-tris(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)ethane 72, 1,1,5-bis[2,2-dichloro-1-(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)ethanyl]-2,4-dimethoxybenzene 73, 1,1,1,2,2-pentakis(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)ethane 74 besides 2,2-dichloro-1,1-bis(2,4-

dimethoxyphenyl)ethylene 75 and 1,1-bis(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)ethylene 76. The structure 73 is the revised structure of compound 7 in reference 40 on the basis of its NMR spectroscopic data and consideration of its mechanism of formation⁴². The predominant formation of the *m*-oriented products 2,2-dichloro-1,1-bis(3,5-dimethylphenyl)ethylene 77 and 2-chloro-1,1,2-tris(3-methyl-5-methoxyphenyl)ethylene 78 at higher temperature from the substrates *m*-xylene 79 and *m*-methylanisole 80, respectively, although the methyl group is mainly *ortho/para* directing, has been ascribed to the strenuous condition of the reaction. In general, the more vigorous the reaction conditions (reaction time and temperature, relative amount of catalyst, absence of solvent, etc.), the greater is the tendency toward the formation of *meta* derivatives⁴. Interesting trinuclear compounds 81 and 82 were synthesized using *m*-xylene 79 and 1,3-dimethoxybenzene 71 in excess as substrates and sometimes at high temperature in Friedel-Crafts acylation with dichloroacetyl chloride. The structure of compound 82 was unambiguously determined by single-crystal X-ray analysis, and mechanism of formation of the trinuclear compounds has been rationalised⁴³. The one-step method of preparing such trinuclear compounds is indeed of considerable interest.

A novel application of the Friedel-Crafts acylation reaction with dichloroacetyl chloride to the synthesis of differently substituted polynuclear compounds using different pairs of substituted benzenes has been published⁴⁴. The substrates used for the study were mono- and disubstituted benzenes of varying nucleophilicity, e.g. toluene, chlorobenzene, anisole, phenetole, *m*-xylene and 1,3-dimethoxybenzene. Initially, the reaction was carried out under Friedel-Crafts conditions with nucleophile of lower reactivity using stoichiometric proportions of the reactants

and the catalyst to facilitate the formation of the normal acylated product. Application of higher temperature was necessary for stimulating the reaction for the substrates of lower reactivity. No solvent was necessary for the initial acylation reaction as all the substrates used were liquids. But for the reaction of the acylated product and the second substrate, CS_2 was used as solvent. Thus the binuclear compounds **83-86** were synthesized by the use of anisole and phenetole, anisole and 1,3-dimethoxybenzene, toluene and 1,3-dimethoxybenzene, toluene and anisole, and chlorobenzene and anisole, respectively. By increasing the proportion of the second substrate used in the later stage of the reaction to bimolar or higher, mixed tetranuclear products **87, 88** were prepared in moderate yields. The interesting trinuclear products **89** and **90** comprising *m*-xylene and anisole as well as *m*-xylene and 1,3-dimethoxybenzene were synthesized when the respective pairs of the substrates were subjected to similar treatment in the prescribed reaction conditions. The structure of compounds **88** and **90** were unambiguously determined by single-crystal X-ray analysis. The mechanism of formation of the products were also rationalized⁴⁴. The results strongly supported the new concept propounded by the authors that the formation of the unexpected secondary products depends on the nucleophilicity of the substrate and electrophilicity of the acyl carbonyl group of the initially formed acylated product and that this acylated product reacts with the other nucleophile if present in the reaction mixture.

The results amply demonstrated that dichloroacetyl chloride and various substituted arenes may be utilized under Friedel-Crafts conditions for the convenient synthesis of differently substituted polynuclear compounds of pharmaceutical interest. By proper regulation of reaction parameters, it is possible to synthesize targeted compounds, and the method has potential for wider application.

The method of using excess amounts of the substrates and high temperature under Friedel-Crafts reaction condition was employed for the synthesis of novel indolylquinolines **91-95**. Indole or its 5-substituted derivatives were used as substrates and dichloroacetyl chloride, chloroacetyl chloride and acetyl chloride as acylating agents⁴⁵. The synthesis of indolylquinolines from indole or its derivatives had not been reported earlier. This one-step approach to the synthesis of these analogs appears to be attractive for its preparative simplicity. The structures of these compounds were unequivocally established by X-ray crystallographic analysis. A mechanism (Scheme 2) for the formation of the compounds was also rationalized. Inhibitory effects of three indolyl quinolines **91, 93** and **95** on topoisomerases from *Leishmania* were investigated⁴⁶. The

Scheme 2

compounds inhibit the relaxation and decatenation reactions catalyzed by type I and type II DNA topoisomerases of *Leishmania donovani*. The results indicated that the compounds act as dual inhibitors of the enzymes and can be exploited for rational drug design in human leishmaniasis. These indolylquinoline derivatives were found to be cytotoxic to *L. donovani* promastigotes and amastigotes *in vitro* and effective in treating murine visceral leishmaniasis⁴⁷. The 2-, and 3-methylindole analogs **96-99** and 3-methylindole dimers **100, 101** of biological interest were synthesized in one-step using excess amounts of the substrates and the catalyst under Friedel-Crafts acylation con-

ditions. The structures of the products were unambiguously defined by single crystal X-ray analysis and rationalization for their formation was also attempted⁴⁸.

3-Substituted pyrroles and 3-acylindoles

3-Substituted pyrroles, particularly 3-alkylpyrroles have been investigated as starting monomers for the

preparation of organic conducting materials⁴⁹, as well as precursors in porphyrin chemistry⁵⁰. Rokach *et al.*⁵¹ developed a simple and efficient synthesis of 3-acylated

pyrroles. The method involves preparation of *N*-phenylsulfonylpyrrole **103** from pyrrole **102** followed by its AlCl_3 catalyzed acylations with various acylating agents and subsequent removal of the phenylsulfonyl group by mild basic hydrolysis (eq 15). The method is attractive because of the regioselectivity in the Friedel-Crafts acylation step as well as high overall yield. Pyrroles generally undergo substitution at the C-2 position. But in *N*-phenylsulfonylpyrrole Friedel-Crafts acylations take place at the C-3 position. This differential reactivity has been interpreted⁵² in terms of hard and soft acids and bases principle⁵³. The CNDO calculations indicate that the greater negative charge in *N*-phenylsulfonylpyrrole is located at C-3 and the higher HOMO coefficient is at C-2⁵². Thus, invoking Klopman's general treatment of chemical reactivity,⁵⁴ reaction with hard electrophiles is apparently charge controlled and occurs at C-3, while reaction with soft electrophiles is frontier orbital controlled and occurs at C-2.

Another simple method for the synthesis of 3-acylated pyrrole⁵⁵ involves the use of 1-*tert*-butyldimethylsilyl (TBDMS) pyrrole which undergoes Friedel-Crafts acylation almost exclusively at the 3-position giving after

sodium fluoride supported hydrolysis the 3-pyrroloketones (eq. 16).

A suitable method for the synthesis of 3-ethenylpyrroles has been developed starting from 3-acetyl-1-tosylpyrroles. This easy accessibility to the 3-ethenylpyrroles makes this compound a convenient source of other 3-substituted pyrrole derivatives. The useful substrate, 3-vinylpyrrole 113 was synthesized⁵⁶ (eq. 17).

Friedel-Crafts acylations of 3-alkyl-1-(phenylsulfonyl)pyrroles is kinetically favoured at the C-2 position but rearrangement to the C-5 position can occur after prolonged reaction times. This property was utilized for the synthesis of ant trail pheromone, methyl 4-methylpyrrole-2-carboxylate 117⁵⁷ (eq. 18).

A convenient synthesis of 3-acylindoles 118 via Friedel-Crafts acylation of 1-(phenylsulfonyl)indole 119 was developed by Ketcha and Gribble⁵⁸. Although the addition of electrophiles to the C-3 position of indole is a common phenomenon, the synthesis of 3-acylindoles is often complicated by the competing substitution at nitrogen. The above method involves a Friedel-Crafts acylation of 119 with carboxylic acid anhydrides and acid chlorides in the presence of AlCl₃ to give 3-acyl-1-(phenylsulfonyl)indoles 120 which on base-hydrolysis furnishes 3-acylindoles 118. Acylation of 119 with acid chloride 121 in presence of AlCl₃ gives 122 which on strong-base-mediated cyclization yields 123. Since quinone 123 has been previously converted to the anticancer alkaloid ellipticine 124⁵⁹ this route to 123 represents a new synthesis of ellipticine 124 (eq. 19).

Stereoselective synthesis

The synthesis of optically pure α -aminoalkyl aryl ketones is of much interest because it provides a direct route to a large variety of biologically active compounds containing the phenylethylamine moiety in their active, asymmetric configurations. Buckley III and Rapoport⁶⁰ developed α -*N*-acylamino acids as useful reagents for the preparations of optically pure α -aminoalkyl aryl ketones. Protection of the amino group as either the ethoxycarbonyl or benzenesulfonyl derivative makes it an effective educt for the chirally specific synthesis of a variety of structures containing the phenylethylamine backbone. Amino acids substituted in this way may be used to acylate benzene or alkoxybenzenes. Benzene undergoes Friedel-Crafts acylation with the *N*-acylalanine acid chloride. However, problem was encountered for Friedel-Crafts acylation of aryl ethers which was overcome by arylmetal reaction using aryllithium reagent or arylmagnesium bromide. Thus all the acylations proceeded with complete retention of asymmetry. The ketone carbonyl was then subjected to further structural development without any racemization at the amino carbon. For example, *L*-*N*-ethoxycarbonylalanine 125 was converted to its acid chloride 126, which on Friedel-Crafts reaction with benzene in presence of AlCl₃ (200 mol%) yielded the desired ketocarbamate 127 in high yield (eq. 20). The product 127 was readily isolated and shown to be optically pure. Its optical purity was confirmed by complete reduction of 127 followed by diastereoisomer analysis of the resulting *N*-methylamine.

The same authors⁶¹ achieved chirally specific total syntheses of tylophorine and cryptopleurine, the major representatives of the phenanthroindolizidine and phenanthro-

quinolizidine alkaloids respectively from *S*- α -aminoacids as educts. A key intramolecular Friedel-Crafts acylation was successfully utilized to produce both the tylophorine and cryptopleurine ring systems optically intact. The *N*-(phenanthrylmethyl) glutamate **128** on cyclization in warm MeOH/HOAc afforded amido ester **129** which in turn was hydrolyzed to amido acid **130** in good overall yield. The amido acid **130** was converted to acid chloride **131** which was cyclized to the optically active tetramethoxyketone **132** in nearly quantitative yield by the action of SnCl₄ in refluxing CH₂Cl₂ without any demethylation. The amido ketone **132** was further elaborated to tylophorine **133** (eq. 21).

The alkylated diester **134** was hydrolyzed to the diacid **135** which was cyclized readily in boiling water to amido acid **136**. The amido acid chloride **137** on Friedel-Crafts intramolecular acylation by the action of SnCl₄ in refluxing CH₂Cl₂ was converted to the amido ketone **138**. The optically active cryptopleurine **139** was obtained by further elaboration of the amido ketone **138** (eq. 22). Both alkaloids tylophorine **133** and cryptopleurine **139** derived from (*S*)- α -amino acids were dextrorotatory and exhibited positive CD curves⁶¹.

McClure *et al.*⁶² described a novel and preparatively useful approach to chiral α -amino ketones via a Friedel-Crafts reaction of *N*-protected amino acids. The retention of chirality was shown to be dependent upon the utilization of the *N*-methoxycarbonyl derivative. For example, the methoxycarbonyl derivative **140** via its acid chloride produced **141** (eq. 23). The respective chiral precursors furnished (*R*)- or (*S*)-**141** after an aqueous hydrochloric acid work-up. Chiral shift NMR analysis⁶³ with Eu(hfc)₃ disclosed none of the opposite enantiomer indicating a chiral purity of $\geq 98\%$ for each isomer.

In an investigation by the authors⁶² of the corresponding intermolecular Friedel-Crafts reaction, the retention of chirality was quite high. The reaction of the acid chloride from *N*-(methoxycarbonyl)alanine [**142** or (*S*)-**142**] and benzene under AlCl₃ catalysis gave the acyclic *N*-protected α -aminoketone [**143** or (*S*)-**143**] as an oil (eq. 24). Chiral shift NMR analysis disclosed the presence of only 3–4% of the corresponding *R*-isomer. Thus the retention of chirality is synthetically useful in both the intra- and intermolecular modes.

Evidently, this approach to the synthesis of chiral vicinal aminoketones which depends on high enantiomeric retention in the Friedel-Crafts reaction is an extremely valuable addition to the synthetic techniques in organic and medicinal chemistry.

Chiral *N*-(trifluoroacetyl)- α -amino acid chlorides **144** undergo Friedel-Crafts reaction with benzene and 1,2-dimethoxybenzene under mild conditions generally with complete preservation of chirality (eq. 25). This is useful for stereoselective synthesis of similar natural products^{64,65}.

Similarly, *N*-carboxy- α -amino acid anhydrides **146** react with aromatics such as toluene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylene and mesitylene to give α -amino acylated products in moderate yields with complete retention of configuration of the α -amino acid⁶⁶. The α -aminoalkyl aryl ketones are

obtained as free bases **147** or hydrochloride salts **148** (eq. 26).

Miscellaneous synthesis

The formylation of aromatic compounds such as benzene, toluene, xylenes, mesitylene, indan, tetralin, fluorobenzene, chlorobenzene and bromobenzene in $\text{HSO}_3\text{F}\cdot\text{SbF}_5$ under atmospheric CO pressure at 0° was disclosed by Tanaka *et al.*⁶⁷. In this system both formylation and sulfonation took place to give formyl and sulfonyl compounds. Alkylbenzenesulfonyl fluorides as well as alkylbenzaldehydes, alkylbenzenesulfonyl fluorides, and bis(alkylphenyl)sulfones were produced using alkylbenzenes, including toluene, xylenes, mesitylene and tetralin as substrates. The formyl group was exclusively introduced into the *para*-position of the alkyl group in all cases and the sulfonyl group was introduced into the *meta*-position of the formyl group. For example, when *o*-xylene **149** was added to a mixture of HSO_3F and SbF_5 with vigorous stirring under atmospheric CO pressure at 0° , alkylbenzaldehyde **150** as well as formylalkylbenzenesulfonyl fluoride **151** were obtained by a one-pot reaction (eq. 27). Apparently, the reaction path is a two-step process consisting of formylation as the first step and sulfonation as the second step.

An efficient method for alkylation of aromatics was developed⁶⁸ by Friedel-Crafts acylation with branched or polyfunctionalised acyl halides followed by *in situ* reduction of the resulting carbonyl-Lewis acid complex with triethylsilane or polymethylhydrosiloxane (PMHS) polymer. The alkylated aromatic products were obtained in high yield in contrast to the low yield and byproducts problem in direct aromatic alkylation.

Anhydrous hydrogen fluoride catalyzed Friedel-Crafts acylation was investigated by Aslam *et al.*⁶⁹. The catalyst was found to be effective for the acylation of (alkyl-

thio)aromatics to the corresponding acylation products. Thioanisole **152** reacted with acetic anhydride in presence of anhydrous HF to yield **153** in >90% yield.

Dibenzofuran (DBF) **154** is a key industrial intermediate and its chemistry has attracted much attention⁷⁰. Isomer distribution of DBF in Friedel-Crafts acylations, alkylations and nitrations were determined⁷¹. The 2- and 3-positions of DBF represent most of the total reactivity. The positional reactivities were found to be in the order, 2- > 3- > 1- > 4- for acylations, benzylations, and nitrations with alkyl nitrate/Lewis acid or nitronium tetrafluoroborate. However, for nitration of DBF with nitric acid, a different reactivity order of 3- > 2- > 1- > 4- was found. In particular, nitration with nitric acid in CH_2Cl_2 gave mostly 3-nitro-DBF. The authors concluded from MNDO calculations that the late transition-state model (by σ -complex) favours reaction at the 2-position and the early transition-state model (by HOMO electron density) leads to the 3-substitution.

Friedel-Crafts acylation was investigated on several acid-sensitive substrates⁷². It was found that by proper selection of the Lewis acid, solvent and reaction temperature, the acylation reaction can occur using very sensitive substrates and acylating agents with reasonable efficiency. Thus the 5-hydroxy derivative **155** reacted with **156** or **157** in presence of TiCl_4 in CH_2Cl_2 at -78° to give **158** or **159**, respectively. Formylation of **158** and **159** occurred on treatment with bis(dimethylamino)-*tert*-butoxymethane to produce calopogonium isoflavone-B **160** and jamaicin **161**, respectively (eq. 28).

Ohwada *et al.*⁷³ examined the Friedel-Crafts reaction of 1,2-dione such as 2,3-butadione **162** with benzene in the

presence of trifluoromethanesulfonic acid (TFSA) and obtained the product 3,3-diphenyl-2-butanone **163**. The product is apparently formed through diphenylation of one of the carbonyl groups. 2,3-Butanedione monoxime **164** reacted with benzene in the presence of a large amount of TFSA to give the monophenylated ene oxime **165** together with diphenylated oxime **166**. The monophenyl product **165** was derived by the C₁-phenylation of the ketoxime **164** and the diphenyl product **166** was formed by double phenylation of the C₁ position, as in the reaction of 2,3-butanedione **162**. The reactive electrophiles in these Friedel-Crafts reactions are considered to be *O,O*-diprotonated 1,2-dicarbonyl species and *N,O*-diprotonated ketoxime, i.e. related ethylene dications differentiated by a single different heteroatom substituent, a hydroxy or a hydroxyamino group⁷³.

Acylation of aliphatic and alicyclic compounds

Aliphatic and alicyclic compounds also undergo Friedel-Crafts reactions. Strenuous reaction conditions that are used in the acylation of olefins can be avoided in suitable cases by the incorporation of silyl group. For example, acylation of trialkylsilylolefins under mild Friedel-Crafts conditions produce α,β -unsaturated ketones by replacement of the trialkylsilyl group by the acyl group⁷⁴. These reactions are highly regioselective. 2-Methylcyclobutenyltrimethylsilane **167** on Friedel-Crafts acylation yields 2-methyl-1-acetylcyclobutene **168** which was used as an intermediate in the synthesis of grandisol **169**⁷⁵ (eq. 29).

Condensation of cyclohexene **170** with crotonyl chloride produces the cyclopentenone derivative **171** as one of the products which is an important precursor of terpenoids⁷⁶ (eq. 30).

Cyclododecene **172** (*cis* and *trans*) reacts slowly with crotonyl bromide at -78° to give ketone **173** which is an important intermediate in the synthesis of \pm muscone **174**, a valuable perfumary product⁷⁶ (eq. 31).

Intramolecular Friedel-Crafts acylations of olefins also give α,β -unsaturated cyclic ketones. Paquette and Hun Ham⁷⁷ successfully converted acid chloride **175** predominantly to cyclopentenone **176** by Friedel-Crafts cyclization which was subsequently transformed to the marine sesquiterpenes africanol **177** and dactyolol **178** (eq. 32).

Allylsilanes undergo regioselective acylation producing β,γ -unsaturated ketones⁷⁸. Acylation of γ,γ -dialkylallyl-trialkylsilane gives a β,γ -unsaturated ketone with a quaternary carbon centre (eq. 33).

The ω -trimethylsilylethynyl alkanoyl chlorides undergo macrocyclization in high dilution condition to give 11-15-membered cyclic yrones which are used as intermediates in the synthesis of muscone⁷⁹. The regioselectivity of the reaction is evidently influenced by the β -carbocation stabilizing influence of the silicon substituent.

Olah *et al.*⁸⁰ observed that small alkanes do react with a variety of electrophiles in super acid media under mild conditions. However, in this process isomeric carboxylic acids are produced as a mixture. Delavarenne *et al.*⁸¹ developed halogen-promoted selective carbonylation of propane in super acid media. When the reaction was carried out with catalytic amounts of bromine in HF-SbF₅ solution, regioselective carboxylation was obtained. Thus *n*-propane was converted almost exclusively to isobutyric acid. Other reports of direct carbonylation of saturated alkanes in super acid media include the reactions of C₆ cycloalkanes⁸² and C₅-C₈ cycloalkanes⁸³ as well as adamantane **179**⁸⁴.

Several reports have appeared on nitration of adamantane **179**. Moiseev *et al.*^{85,86} observed formation of 1-

adamantyl nitrate in the reaction of adamantane with nitric acid. Adamantane also reacted with bromine in nitric acid to produce 1-nitroadamantane as a minor product⁸⁷. Low yield nitration of adamantane with nitronium salts in aprotic solvents at ambient temperature was reported⁸⁸. The slow reaction of adamantane with nitronium tetrafluoroborate at room temperature in nitrite-free nitromethane or nitroethane gave 1-nitroadamantane **180** in 66 and 74% yield, respectively⁸⁹. Diamantane **181** under similar reaction conditions yielded 62% 1-nitrodiamantane **182** and 5% 4-nitrodiamantane **183**. The experimental data indicate the intermediate formation of the adamantyl cation followed by reaction with HNO_2 or NO_2 formed in the reaction, giving 1-adamantyl nitrite, which then undergoes cleavage-rearrangement to give 1-nitroadamantane.

Friedel-Crafts catalysts

Lewis acids :

The widely used Lewis acids in Friedel-Crafts chemistry are halides of different metals and the most frequently used catalysts are AlCl_3 , AlBr_3 and BF_3 . Lewis acid catalysts were divided into four categories : very active, moderately active, weak and very weak, on the basis of their relative catalytic activity as evaluated by comparison with alkylating ability of benzyl chloride⁹⁰. Boron, aluminium, and gallium tris(trifluoromethanesulfonate)(triflates) $\text{M}(\text{OTf})_3$ prepared from the corresponding chlorides (bromides) and triflic acid by Olah *et al.*⁹¹ were found to be efficient new Friedel-Crafts catalysts in alkylation, isomerization and acylation reactions under mild conditions. Boron triflate due to its high activity, good solubility, but more limited thermal stability, is the preferred catalysts in solution under mild conditions, whereas aluminium and gallium triflates are applicable as solid or support Friedel-Crafts catalysts.

Bismuth tris-trifluoromethanesulfonate [$\text{Bi}(\text{OTf})_3$] was found to be a novel catalyst for the Friedel-Crafts acylation⁹². The reaction of activated or deactivated benzenes proceeded with high yields in the presence of a catalytic amount of $\text{Bi}(\text{OTf})_3$. The catalyst is water-stable and its catalytic activity appeared to be much higher than the other metallic triflates such as those of Al, Ga, La or Sc.

Protic acids (Brönsted acids) :

In Friedel-Crafts reactions sulfuric acid is among the frequently used Brönsted acids. Anhydrous HF is also a convenient protic acid but its industrial use is limited for environmental problems caused by its toxic hazardous nature. Acids are electron acceptors and in that sense there is no difference between Brönsted and Lewis acids. However, it may be mentioned that only non-bonded electron pair donors, viz. alkylhalides can readily coordinate with Lewis acid catalysts, i.e. AlCl_3 or BF_3 , whereas with bonded electron pair donors, such as olefins and aromatics, protic acid catalysts are necessary.

Superacids :

Perchloric acid (HClO_4) was first called superacid due to its ability to protonate weak organic bases such as ketones and aldehydes⁹³. According to Gillespie *et al.*^{94,95}, all protic acids stronger than 100% sulfuric acid are superacids. By this definition perchloric acid, fluorosulfonic acid (HSO_3F) and trifluoromethanesulfonic acid ($\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3\text{H}$) are categorized to be superacids.

Lewis superacids :

Superacidity encompasses both Brönsted and Lewis acids. Acid systems which are stronger than anhydrous AlCl_3 are classified as Lewis superacids⁹⁶. These systems include SbF_5 , NbF_5 , AsF_5 and TaF_5 .

Brönsted-Lewis superacids :

Conjugate Friedel-Crafts acids prepared from protic and Lewis acids are superacids. Acid systems prepared from a pentafluoride of group V elements, particularly SbF_5 and a strong protic acid such as HF, FSO_3H , $\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3\text{H}$, etc. are highly acidic systems. For example, magic acid ($\text{HSO}_3\text{F-SbF}_5$), fluoroantimonic acid (HF-SbF_5), $\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3\text{H-SbF}_5$ and $\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3\text{H-B}(\text{OTf})_3$ are highly effective catalysts. An excellent review on super acids by Olah *et al.*⁹⁷ discusses measurement of acidity H_0 , preparation and application of such acid systems.

Zeolites :

Zeolites are drawing much attention in a wide range of contexts, particularly in the area of catalysis⁹⁸. These are salts of solid silicoaluminic acids characterized by a strictly regular structure of their crystalline lattice⁹⁹ and belonging to acid type catalysts. The acid form of zeolites are important in a variety of catalytic reactions¹⁰⁰⁻¹⁰². Zeolites as catalysts for selective organic transformations are drawing considerable attention recently due to their unique physical and chemical properties, such as shape selectivity, acidity and thermal stability^{103,104}. The catalytic potential of zeolites has been exploited for organic transformations,

such as conversion of spirolactones to the corresponding enones, synthesis of polynuclear aromatic compounds and aromatic 3-Aza-Cope rearrangements¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁷. There are some examples in the literature of the utilization of zeolite catalysts for the acylation of aromatics¹⁰⁸⁻¹¹³. Chiche *et al.*¹⁰⁸ reported catalytic acylation of toluene and *p*-xylene by different carboxylic acids over a Y-type zeolite, particularly by using long-chain fatty acids. The best catalyst they found was a Y-faujasite-type zeolite [Na₅₆(AlO₂)₅₆(SiO₂)₁₃₆.nH₂O] exchanged with Ce³⁺ cation. The interesting feature they observed was the excellent selectivity in the acylation of toluene where with all acids studied, the yield of *para*-isomer was at least 94%.

The high positional selectivity observed in these zeolite catalyzed electrophilic aromatic substitution was explained by invoking the shape-selectivity of zeolites which is due to the shape of channels : the *ortho*-isomer might not be formed due to a lack of space within the channel or cavity. Hy and Hb zeolites were used in the acylation of anisole by phenylacetyl and phenylpropionyl chloride¹⁰⁹. The *p*-acylated products were obtained without any noticeable demethylation.

Sreekumar and Padmakumar¹¹² reported a convenient heterogeneous catalytic methodology for Friedel-Crafts acylation of benzene and toluene using various aliphatic carboxylic acid anhydrides over HY-zeolite and HZSM-5 at 250°. In the acylation of toluene, the most interesting feature was the excellent selectivity for *para*-acylated product over HZSM-5. These authors also attributed the high positional selectivity in HZSM-5 catalyzed electrophilic aromatic substitutions to shape selectivity.

Spagnol *et al.*¹¹³ demonstrated that anisole and veratrole could be efficiently acylated at the *para*-position in liquid phase by acetic anhydride with zeolite catalysts such as HZSM-5, H-Mordenite, Hb and Hy under mild conditions without demethylation¹¹³. The pore size of the zeolite was found to be a critical parameter for a good reactivity. These authors correlated the reactivity with pore sizes by comparing the volume of the Weyland's Friedel-Crafts intermediates and the intersection of the pore sizes of the catalyst. By using NMR techniques it was shown that acetic anhydride is better activated by Brønsted acid whereas acyl chlorides are well activated by Lewis acids.

A series of aromatic ketones such as 4-acylanisole were prepared with high yield by using carboxylic acid as acylating agents and HY zeolite as catalyst¹¹⁴.

Conclusion

The contributions of Friedel-Crafts chemistry to syn-

thetic organic chemistry are remarkable. The wide scope of the reaction which was realized even in the early stage of its discovery has enlarged tremendously during the years and it has been utilized as key steps in many organic synthetic ventures. Many important industrial processes are based on Friedel-Crafts chemistry. Although advances in the area of preparative organic chemistry are already significant, further developments relating to yield, selectivity, efficiency, suitability to environment, economy and discovery of new useful reaction types are anticipated. Increasing use of highly acidic solid catalysts such as HZSM-5, an acidic form of zeolite or high molecular weight perfluoroalkanesulfonic acids such as perfluorodecanesulfonic acid, CF₃(CF₂)₉SO₃H for conducting Friedel-Crafts reactions particularly in industrial processes is a distinct possibility.

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